

**THE EFFECT AND ADVANTAGES OF USING GRAMMAR
TRANSLATION METHOD TO ON LEARNING AS A FOREIGN
LANGUAGE****Nizomova Zebiniso Rustamjon kizi**

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Learning second language is a global occurrence. To find suitable methods to enable learning process is anxiety. The question that creates an obvious disagreement between EFL researchers is that: shall the teachers use only second language within classroom's setting? And a lot of studies have been conducted in which they showed different results as to whether translation helps second language students improve their language skills or not. Some teachers consider using first language within L2 classroom setting causes a huge harm on learning L2 while others recommend teachers to use it. These debates do not conclude to one conclusion yet.

Foreign languages translation process or learning second language is not only the process of expressing meaning from the native language to the target language, the profit of translation go further. It is pedagogic method that makes easier learning of four language skills and make a foreign language more understandable to English language learners, especially in their first levels of learning.

In addition to the four skills in any language, the grammar is an elementary base. Teaching English grammar provides crystal clear frame to guarantee producing right structures and accelerate the process of learning.

A grammar translation is one of the most successful methods that focuses on translating the sentences which indicates grammatical rules to learn English as a second language. This method was used a long time ago in order to teach Latin as a second language. Being preferred after studied German in the 19th century it began to recommend.

Many surveys have bees organized on the area of using GRM and translation in teaching L2. These studies developed a lot the developed control of teaching language. Different studies try to demonstrate that translation method is one of the most profitable pedagogic applicable to the teachers. Like, Dagilienė (2012) conducted a survey in Kaunas to investigate the role of translation as a learning method in English

language teaching. The sample included of 78 third year students from the faculty of Design and Technologies at Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), the study found out that translation is a useful tool in English language course which intensify the skills of second language students.

Al Refaai (2013) conducted a research about suggested guidelines for using translation in foreign language and teaching. The study was carried in the English language center (ELC) in King Khalid university, Saudi Arabia. The sample consisted 19 teachers who are native speakers of Arabic and who teaching English at basic level. The findings show that the translation enhance the competence and right performance of language, it is a preferable method for both teachers and students, and using the L1 alongside the L2 fulfills the needs of the students.

In Jordan, the big concern of language teachers and researchers is to improve the students' achievement in learning English as a second language, especially grammar, the low level of students in grammar points the existence of such problem. This study attempts to figure out if the Grammar-Translation method can help students to move forward in learning process, explore the students' attitude toward this method. And distinguish the benefits are gained from monolingual or bilingual EFL classrooms (Al Khotaba and Ahmad, 20). There are many advantages of translation method. Firstly, GTM helps the students to read and appreciate target language literature. As a result students' writing and reading skills can be well trained. Additionally, with the help of learning grammar rules students' reading skills are strengthened and making up correct sentences is enabled. Learning grammar rules plays an important role in GRM and this method is useful for learners who decided to become skillful in writing and reading skills.

There are also many handy ways of this method. It helps teachers much to clear the meaning of a word and sentence to the students easily by translating them in to the L1. Moreover it is beneficial to use in the class where there are students of various levels- very intelligent and not-so- very intelligent.

The research findings indicate that Grammar-Translation method is an important kind of teaching methodology that the teachers should adapt it to teach English as a second language and the researchers should highlight the advantage or disadvantage of this method. Many reasons are behind that, first, because it is an applicable method and easy to conduct. Second, the first intellectual act the learner can use when feel unable to express by the target language is interpreting by native language and that exactly the core of this method. Third, the great benefit of join the knowledge of both languages which free the learner from the ambiguity of the target language. After all, the researcher recommend that after the exhibiting of the language skills and the grammatical rules, the usefulness of translation is decreasing. Therefore, the applying of grammatical structure or the practicing of the language skills in general should be in the target language to confirm the needed forms that the learners must develop to achieve the best results they are looking for.

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